

Caspase Selective Reagents for Diagnosing Apoptotic Mechanisms

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SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Table S1 Structures of biotin-labeled activity based probes selected for apoptotic caspases based on the HyCoSuL screening data.

BROAD SPECTRUM CASPASE PROBES

biotin-ahx-Asp-Glu-Val-Asp-AOMK
DEV D-AOMK

biotin-ahx-Leu-Glu-His-Asp-AOMK
LEHD-AOMK

biotin-ahx-Ile-Glu-Thr-Asp-AOMK
IETD-AOMK

biotin-ahx-Leu-Gln-Nle-Asp-AOMK
LQnD

CASPASE-3, -7 SELECTIVE

biotin-ahx-Asp-Phe(F₅)-Val-Asp-AOMK
bMP-3.01

CASPASE-9 SELECTIVE

biotin-ahx-Oic-Tle-His-Asp-AOMK
bMP-9.01

biotin-ahx-Lys(tfa)-Tle-His-Asp-AOMK
bMP-9.02

biotin-ahx-Lys(Ac)-Tle-His-Asp-AOMK
bMP-9.03

biotin-ahx-Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-His-Asp-AOMK
bMP-9.04

biotin-ahx-Oic-Tle-His(Bzl)-Asp-AOMK
bMP-9.05

biotin-ahx-Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-Ala-Asp-AOMK
bMP-9.06

biotin-ahx-Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-Ala-Ser-AOMK
bMP-9.07

biotin-ahx-Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-Ala-Thr-AOMK
bMP-9.08

CASPASE-8 SELECTIVE

biotin-ahx-DhPhe-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Asp-AOMK
bMP-8.10

biotin-ahx-DIgl-hGlu-Thr-Asp-AOMK
bMP-8.11

biotin-ahx-D2-Nal-hGlu-His-Asp-AOMK
bMP-8.01

biotin-ahx-DTyr(Bzl)l-hGlu-His-Asp-AOMK
bMP-8.02

biotin-ahx-*D*Phe(4-F)-hGlu-His-Asp-AOMK
bMP-8.03

biotin-ahx-*D*2-Nal-hGlu-Thr-Asp-AOMK
bMP-8.04

biotin-ahx-*D*Phe(3,4-Cl₂)-hGlu-Thr-Asp-AOMK
bMP-8.05

biotin-ahx-*D*Phe(3,4-F₂)-hGlu-Thr-Asp-AOMK
bMP-8.06

biotin-ahx-*D*2-Nal-hGlu-Ala-Asp-AOMK
bMP-8.07

biotin-ahx-*D*Phe(3,4-Cl₂)-hGlu-Ala-Asp-AOMK
bMP-8.08

biotin-ahx-*D*Phe(4-F)-hGlu-Ala-Asp-AOMK
bMP-8.09

CASPASE-10 SELECTIVE

biotin-ahx-Leu-Lys(tfa)-Ser(Bzl)-Asp-AOMK
bMP-10.01

biotin-ahx-hLeu-Gln-Ser-Asp-AOMK
bMP-10.02

biotin-ahx-Nle(O-Bzl)-Gln-Ser-Asp-AOMK
bMP-10.03

biotin-ahx-Nle(O-Bzl)-Glu-Ser-Asp-AOMK
bMP-10.04

biotin-ahx-Nle(O-Bzl)-Glu-Gln-Asp-AOMK
bMP-10.05

biotin-ahx-hLeu-Glu-Gln-Asp-AOMK
bMP-10.06

biotin-ahx-Nle(O-Bzl)-Dab-Gln-Asp-AOMK
bMP-10.07

biotin-ahx-Nle(O-Bzl)-Gln-Glu-Asp-AOMK
bMP-10.08

biotin-ahx-Nle(*O*-Bzl)-Thr(Bzl)-Glu-Asp-AOMK
bMP-10.09

biotin-ahx-Leu-Dab-Glu-Asp-AOMK
bMP-10.10

biotin-ahx-Leu-Dab-Ser(Bzl)-Asp-AOMK
bMP-10.11

biotin-ahx-Leu-Lys(tfa)-Ser(Bzl)-Asp-AOMK
bMP-10.12

biotin-ahx-Nle-hArg-hPhe-Asp-AOMK
bMP-10.13

biotin-ahx-Nle-Dab-Ser(Bzl)-Asp-AOMK
bMP-10.14

Table S2 Kinetic parameters (k_{obs}/I , $M^{-1}s^{-1}$) of biotin-labeled probes measured toward five human apoptotic caspases (-3, -7, -8, -9, and -10); r.i. – reversible inhibition; n.i. – no inhibition ($k_{\text{obs}}/I < 10 M^{-1}s^{-1}$). SD for all parameters were below 20%. Cysteine cathepsins L and B were only poorly inhibited by the ABPs (k_{obs}/I parameters for all ABPs were below $200 M^{-1}s^{-1}$).

b-ahx-peptide-AOMK	Code bMP-x	k_{obs}/I , $M^{-1}s^{-1}$						
		Casp-2	Casp-3	Casp-6	Casp-7	Casp-8	Casp-9	Casp-10
broad spectrum								
LEHD	-	4,870	86,000	29,800	26,500	465,000	18,500	118,000
DEVD	-	26,100	5,600,000	109,000	1,250,000	255,000	8,920	76,300
IETD	-	11,600	420,000	219,000	12,300	322,000	2,050	121,000
LQnD	-	26,400	230,000	15,200	14,800	425,000	4,250	143,000
caspase-3/7 selective								
DFVD	3.01	1,450	3,260,000	15,700	1,120,000	134,000	1,970	7,500
caspase-9 selective								
Oic-Tle-His	9.01	n.i.	340	18	75	r.i.	r.i.	1,850
Lys(tfa)-Tle-His	9.02	41	6,500	45	528	r.i.	r.i.	1,560
Lys(ac)-Tle-His	9.03	n.i.	5,350	54	428	r.i.	r.i.	2,100
Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-His	9.04	n.i.	410	12	25	r.i.	r.i.	1,888
Oic-Tle-His(Bzl)	9.05	n.i.	484	28	36	r.i.	r.i.	560
Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-Ala	9.06	837	6,600	64	279	6,500	14,200	2,210
Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-Ser	9.07	n.i.	2,540	30	42	1,350	8,900	1,560
Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-Thr	9.08	45	4,800	112	28	2,700	2,100	1,700
caspase-8 selective								
D2NaI-hGlu-His	8.01	229	4,400	69	186	r.i.	r.i.	1,250
DTyr(Bzl)-hGlu-His	8.02	90	3,900	32	271	r.i.	r.i.	8,400
DPhe(4-F)-hGlu-His	8.03	117	7,800	92	849	r.i.	r.i.	870
D2NaI-hGlu-Thr	8.04	537	8,900	112	867	96,500	1,240	1,800
DPhe(3,4-Cl ₂)-hGlu-Thr	8.05	319	5,600	219	8,190	22,500	880	1,560
DPhe(3,4-F ₂)-hGlu-Thr	8.06	455	7,300	79	528	18,900	934	1,240
D2NaI-hGlu-Ala	8.07	2,870	9,500	47	747	r.i.	2,770	560
DPhe(3,4Cl ₂)-hGlu-Ala	8.08	2,320	8,900	89	1,230	r.i.	2,370	1,470
DPhe(3,4-F)-hGlu-Ala	8.09	2,300	5,500	57	333	r.i.	4,070	260
DhPhe-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)	8.10	1,210	84,000	3,500	5,200	199,800	4,250	2,560
Dgl-hGlu-Thr	8.11	545	45,500	307	1,800	172,800	5,800	1,450
caspase-10 selective								
Leu-Lys(tfa)-Ser(Bzl)	10.01	5,120	30,700	11,600	810	35,900	2,400	133,000
hLeu-Gln-Ser	10.02	950	2,600	391	1,670	26,500	5,260	166,000
Nle(O-Bzl)-Gln-Ser	10.03	725	4,000	114	1,530	55,000	3,270	70,000
Nle(O-Bzl)-Glu-Ser	10.04	511	12,500	910	3,780	35,600	7,800	109,000
Nle(O-Bzl)-Glu-Gln	10.05	2,660	15,000	2,300	6,100	51,200	6,910	101,500
hLeu-Glu-Gln	10.06	n.i.	8,500	3,570	822	65,500	5,990	143,500
Nle(O-Bzl)-Dab-Gln	10.07	n.i.	300	16	260	16,300	350	44,800
Nle(O-Bzl)-Gln-Glu	10.08	42	270	236	195	45,200	2,400	84,000
Nle(O-Bzl)-Thr(Bzl)-Glu	10.09	89	80	42	69	16,000	560	15,800
Leu-Dab-Glu	10.10	7,100	150	76	25	56,400	890	45,500
Leu-Dab-Ser(Bzl)	10.11	2,940	12,300	2,030	276	26,800	4,400	165,000
Nle-Lys(tfa)-Ser(Bzl)	10.12	4,620	30,700	11,200	842	24,000	2,800	133,000
Nle-hArg-hPhe	10.13	645	2,900	2,590	56	32,500	3,200	64,500
Nle-Dab-Ser(Bzl)	10.14	2,850	5,800	2,060	408	21,000	4,850	74,500

Figure S1 Caspase ABPs display negligible labeling of cathepsin B and L. Panel A and B Labeling of caspase-3, cathepsin L and cathepsin B with a panel of biotin-labeled activity based probes. ABPs (100 nM) were incubated with 50nM of cathepsin L or B, and subjected for SDS-PAGE analysis and proteins were transferred onto membrane. Biotin was detected with fluorescence streptavidin. (Panel A – low sensitivity, Panel B – high sensitivity). **Panel C** The quantification of the enzymes (50nM) labeling by two biotin-tagged ABPs (100nM) - LEHD and DEVD. The y axis shows the intensity signal of the band corresponding to enzyme-ABP complex, and on the x axis investigated proteases are displayed. **Panel D** Inactivation rates (k_{obs}/I , $M^{-1}s^{-1}$) of two biotin-tagged ABPs (LEHD and DEVD) measured against cathepsins-L and -B, and caspases-2, -3, -6, -7, -8, -9, and -10.

Table S3 Kinetic parameters (K_i , nM) of biotin-labeled probes measured toward human caspase-8, and -9. Values were calculated according to Morrison equation. SD for all parameters were below 20%.

b-ahx-(P5)P4P3P2-Asp-AOMK Code bMP-x	K_i , nM		
	Casp-8	Casp-9	
broad spectrum			
LEHD	- irreversible	irreversible	
DEVD	- irreversible	irreversible	
IETD	- irreversible	irreversible	
LQnD	- irreversible	irreversible	
caspase-3/7 selective			
DFVD	3.01 irreversible	irreversible	
caspase-9 selective			
Oic-Tle-His	9.01	38.8	26.6
Lys(tfa)-Tle-His	9.02	157	18.5
Lys(ac)-Tle-His	9.03	133	19.2
Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-His	9.04	145	35.5
Oic-Tle-His(Bzl)	9.05	59.8	116
Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-Ala	9.06	45.3	8.6
Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-Ser	9.07	165	24.5
Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-Thr	9.08	185	13.5
caspase-8 selective			
D2Nal-hGlu-His	8.01	39.9	502
DTyr(Bzl)-hGlu-His	8.02	70.9	630
DPhe(4-F)-hGlu-His	8.03	130	825
D2Nal-hGlu-Thr	8.04	9.2	113
DPhe(3,4-Cl ₂)-hGlu-Thr	8.05	21.8	164
DPhe(3,4-F ₂)-hGlu-Thr	8.06	22.1	101
D2Nal-hGlu-Ala	8.07	35.2	215
DPhe(3,4Cl ₂)-hGlu-Ala	8.08	67.3	533
DPhe(34-F)-hGlu-Ala	8.09	44.8	258
DhPhe-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)	8.10	1.02	237
Dgl-hGlu-Thr	8.11	3.15	68
caspase-10 selective			
Leu-Lys(tfa)-Ser(Bzl)	10.01	42.2	139
hLeu-Gln-Ser	10.02	57.6	108
Nle(O-Bzl)-Gln-Ser	10.03	114	85.6
Nle(O-Bzl)-Glu-Ser	10.04	28	112
Nle(O-Bzl)-Glu-Gln	10.05	25.7	149
hLeu-Glu-Gln	10.06	5.9	226
Nle(O-Bzl)-Dab-Gln	10.07	614	650
Nle(O-Bzl)-Gln-Glu	10.08	58.6	108
Nle(O-Bzl)-Thr(Bzl)-Glu	10.09	160	303
Leu-Dab-Glu	10.10	13.2	311
Leu-Dab-Ser(Bzl)	10.11	14.2	191
Nle-Lys(tfa)-Ser(Bzl)	10.12	51.7	139
Nle-hArg-hPhe	10.13	169	340
Nle-Dab-Ser(Bzl)	10.14	121	244

A

a simplified model of irreversible enzyme inhibition

B

Enzyme	Casp-3	Casp-6	Casp-7	Casp-8	Casp-9	Casp-10
b-LEHD-AOMK	86,000	29,800	26,500	465,000	18,500	118,000

C

$$t_{0.97} = 5 \ln 2 / k_{obs}$$

$t_{0.97}$ - reaction time when 97% of the enzyme is inhibited (5x half-times)

$$t_{0.97} = 1800 \text{ sec} = 5 \ln 2 / k_{obs}$$

$$k_{obs} = 0.001925 \text{ s}^{-1}$$

given that $k_{obs}/[I] = 18,500 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, $[I] = 104 \text{ nM}$

Scheme 1 Calculation of minimal biotin-ahx-LEHD-AOMK concentration to fully inhibit (~97%) each caspase after 30 min incubation, based on the k_{obs}/I parameters. **Panel A** A simplified model of irreversible enzyme inhibition with [EP] reversible intermediate. **Panel B** k_{obs}/I parameter of broad spectrum biotin-ahx-LEHD-AOMK determined against six apoptotic caspases (the lowest affinity was measured for caspase-9). **Panel C** Calculation of minimal ABP concentration to fully inhibit each caspase after 30 min incubation.

Table S4. Structures of substrates and probes for kinetic correlation.

SUBSTRATE	ACTIVITY-BASED PROBE
broad spectrum substrates and probes	
Ac-Asp-Glu-Val-Asp-ACC (Ac-DEVD-ACC)	biotin-ahx-Asp-Glu-Val-Asp-AOMK (b-DEVD-AOMK)
Ac-Leu-Glu-His-Asp-ACC (Ac-LEHD-ACC)	biotin-ahx-Leu-Glu-His-Asp-AOMK (b-LEHD-AOMK)
Ac-Ile-Glu-Thr-Asp-ACC (Ac-IETD-ACC)	biotin-ahx-Ile-Glu-Thr-Asp-AOMK (b-IETD-AOMK)
Ac-Leu-Gln-Nle-Asp-ACC (Ac-LQnD-ACC)	biotin-ahx-Leu-Gln-Nle-Asp-AOMK (b-LQnD-AOMK)
caspase-3/-7 selective substrate and probe	
Ac-Asp-Phe(F ₅)-Val-Asp-ACC (AcMP-3.01-ACC)	biotin-ahx-Asp-Phe(F ₅)-Val-Asp-AOMK (bMP-3.01-AOMK)
caspase-9 selective substrates and probes	
Ac-Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-His-Asp-ACC	biotin-ahx-Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-His-Asp-AOMK

(AcMP-9.04-ACC)

(bMP-9.04-AOMK)

Ac-Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-Ala-Asp-ACC
(AcMP-9.06-ACC)

biotin-ahx-Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-His-Asp-AOMK
(bMP-9.06-AOMK)

Ac-Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-Ser-Asp-ACC
(AcMP-9.07-ACC)

biotin-ahx-Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-Ser-Asp-AOMK
(bMP-9.07-AOMK)

caspase-8 selective substrate and probe

Ac-D2Nal-hGlu-His-Asp-ACC
(AcMP-8.01-ACC)

biotin-ahx-D2Nal-hGlu-His-Asp-AOMK
(bMP-8.01-AOMK)

Ac-D2Nal-hGlu-Thr-Asp-ACC
(AcMP-8.04-ACC)

biotin-ahx-D2Nal-hGlu-Thr-Asp-AOMK
(bMP-8.04-AOMK)

Ac-D2Nal-hGlu-Ala-Asp-ACC
(AcMP-8.07-ACC)

biotin-ahx-D2Nal-hGlu-Ala-Asp-AOMK
(bMP-8.07-AOMK)

Ac-Dlgl-hGlu-Thr-Asp-ACC
(AcMP-8.09-ACC)

biotin-ahx-Dlgl-hGlu-Thr-Asp-AOMK
(bMP-8.09-AOMK)

Ac-DhPhe-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Asp-ACC
(AcMP-8.10-ACC)

biotin-ahx-DhPhe-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Asp-AOMK
(bMP-8.10-AOMK)

caspase-10 selective substrate and probe

Ac-hLeu-Gln-Ser-Asp-ACC
(AcMP-10.02-ACC)

biotin-ahx-hLeu-Gln-Ser-Asp-AOMK
(bMP-10.02-AOMK)

Ac-hLeu-Glu-Gln-Asp-ACC
(AcMP-10.06-ACC)

biotin-ahx-hLeu-Glu-Gln-Asp-AOMK
(bMP-10.06-AOMK)

Ac-Nle(Obzl)-Dab-Gln-Asp-ACC
(AcMP-10.07-ACC)

biotin-ahx-Nle(Obzl)-Dab-Gln-Asp-AOMK
(bMP-10.07-AOMK)

Ac-Leu-Dab-Glu-Asp-ACC
(AcMP-10.10-ACC)

biotin-ahx-Leu-Dab-Glu-Asp-AOMK
(bMP-10.10-AOMK)

Ac-Leu-Dab-Ser(Bzl)-Asp-ACC
(AcMP-10.11-ACC)

biotin-ahx-Leu-Dab-Ser(Bzl)-Asp-AOMK
(bMP-10.11-AOMK)

Table S5 Kinetic parameters (k_{cat}/K_M , $M^{-1}s^{-1}$) for caspase substrates selected for the substrate-probe kinetic correlation studies.

Ac-peptide-Asp-ACC	Code bMP-x	k_{cat}/K_M , $M^{-1}s^{-1}$						
		Casp-2	Casp-3	Casp-6	Casp-7	Casp-8	Casp-9	Casp-10
broad spectrum								
LEHD	-	55	9,670	12,300	667	192,000	12,700	144,000
DEV D	-	340	474,000	1,520	81,700	68,600	310	34,600
IETD	-	< 10	6,120	11,800	422	88,500	2,450	88,200
LQnD	-	41	3,230	280	751	60,100	1,580	107,000
caspase-3/7 selective								
DFVD	3.01	25	181,000	480	40,500	1,500	42	300
caspase-9 selective								
Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-His	9.04	< 10	14	< 10	10	2,410	13,500	1,090
Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-Ala	9.06	< 10	6	< 10	2	5,580	3,160	3,680
Pro-Lys(tfa)-Tle-Ser	9.07	< 10	5	< 10	1	811	3,080	1,560
caspase-8 selective								
D2Nal-hGlu-His	8.01	38	420	650	43	25,700	1,510	328
D2Nal-hGlu-Thr	8.04	< 10	370	< 10	62	10,400	155	382
D2Nal-hGlu-Ala	8.07	< 10	23	< 10	5	3,300	115	127
DhPhe-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)	8.10	< 10	3,400	78	844	82,500	446	1,260
Dlgl-hGlu-Thr	8.11	< 10	734	< 10	167	14,800	358	1,300
caspase-10 selective								
hLeu-Gln-Ser	10.02	33	25	< 10	2	641	414	37,800
hLeu-Glu-Gln	10.06	< 10	59	35	9	1,590	195	38,300
Nle(O-Bzl)-Dab-Gln	10.07	< 10	9	< 10	7	45	10	4,520
Leu-Dab-Glu	10.10	< 10	10	< 10	1	1,200	60	5,700
Leu-Dab-Ser(Bzl)	10.11	< 10	486	125	24	20,800	947	70,900
Nle-Lys(tfa)-Ser(Bzl)	10.12	< 10	580	160	34	11,100	1,100	59,800

Figure S2 The pattern of caspase-3, caspase-8 and PARP processing in TRAIL either etoposide stimulated Jurkat T cells.

Figure S3 Detection of caspases activity in parental, Casp-8^{-/-}, and FADD^{-/-} cells after 8 hours of TRAIL stimulation using DEVD, IETD, and MP-8.01 ACC substrates.

Figure S4 Caspases pull-down experiment using selected ABPs. Caspase-8 and caspase-10 selective biotin-labeled probes (25 μ M) were pre-incubated with Jurkat T cells for 2 hours. After this time all non-internalized probes were washed out and cells were stimulated with TRAIL (100ng/mL) for 8 hours, followed by pulling down all active caspases using streptavidin beads. Captured caspases were detected with specific antiserum (caspase-8) or antibodies (anti-caspase-3 and anti-caspase-10). Pull-down efficiency was correlated with k_{obs}/I parameters of selected ABPs measured against recombinant caspases: “-” $k_{obs}/I < 5,000M^{-1}s^{-1}$, “+” $5,001 < k_{obs}/I < 40,000$, “++” $40,001 < k_{obs}/I < 90,000$, “+++” $90,001 < k_{obs}/I$. Asterisk (*) shows unspecific bands.

Figure S5 Dissecting the mechanism of apoptosis induction in Jurkat T cells using a diverse set of ABPs. **Panel A** The cytotoxicity and pro-survival effect of a diverse set of ABPs tested on TRAIL-stimulated Jurkat T cells. Probes were delivered to cells using reversible permeabilization (RP) procedure or incubating the cells with probes with 4h or 4h+24h, followed by apoptosis induction using TRAIL either etoposide. After 24 hours cell death was measured via cell viability assay. **Panel B** Aggregated table displaying correlation of probe inhibition potency (k_{obs}/I) toward five human apoptotic caspases and cell survival (% ratio to control). Regression coefficients (R²) were calculated from semi-log plot. **Panel C** Scattered plots of correlation of probe inhibition potency (k_{obs}/I) toward five human apoptotic caspases and cell survival (% ratio to control). Regression coefficients (R²) were calculated from semi-log plots, with dotted lines indicating the 95% confidence interval.

Figure S6 Optimization of the probe uptake by Jurkat T cells using digitonin (10 μ g/mL) in RPMI hypotonic medium. Cells were incubated with 1 μ M of fluorescent ABP (FAM-LEHD-AOMK) for indicated time at three RPMI/water hypotonic media. Next cells were centrifuged and allowed to recover for 1 hour. Then the number (and percentage) of live cells was calculated using trypan blue as a staining agent.

Figure S7 Dissecting the mechanism of apoptosis induction in Jurkat T cells using a diverse set of ABPs. **Panel A** Probes were delivered to cells using reversible permeabilization procedure, followed by apoptosis induction using TRAIL either etoposide. After 24 hours cell death was measured via cell viability assay. **Panel B** The cytotoxicity and pro-survival effect of a diverse set of ABPs tested on TRAIL- and etoposide-stimulated Jurkat T cells. **Panel C and D** Correlation between caspase-8 (**C**) and caspase-9 (**D**) probes inhibition potency (K_i) and cell survival (% ratio to control).

Figure S8 Caspase-7 kinetic correlated with TRAIL- or etoposide-stimulated cell death in Jurkat T cells.

Figure S9 Investigation of caspase-9 and caspase-3 activation in cytochrome C-stimulated Jurkat T cell extracts. **Panel A** Inhibition profile of recombinant caspase-3 and caspase-9 by a set of inhibitors and biotin-labeled activity based probes. **Panel B** Western blotting analysis of caspase-3 and caspase-9 activation (and inhibition) upon stimulation of Jurkat T cell extracts with cytochrome c. **Panel C** The kinetic of caspase-3 and caspase-9 activation in Jurkat T cell extracts in the presence of a set of inhibitors/ABPs measured using Ac-DEVD-ACC substrate.

Figure S10 Caspase-8 is mainly responsible for the apoptosis, in TRAIL/birinapant-stimulated MDA-MB-231 human breast cancer cell line. Panel A MDA-MB-231 cells were incubated with 25mM of ABPs for 4 hours prior to apoptosis induction. Then ABPs were washed out (4h) or not (4h+24h), and cells were stimulated with TRAIL (100ng/mL) plus birinapant (2 μ M) for 24 hours. After this time, cells were subjected for cell death assay (MTS assay). Panel B Color-coded index of cell survival outcomes in the presence of diverse ABPs tested in TRAIL+birinapant stimulated MDA-MB-231 cells (*control* – cells incubated with a panel of ABPs (25 μ M) for 4h+24h; *TRAIL+BP, 24h* – cells incubated with ABPs for 4 hours prior to TRAIL/BP stimulation, and for 24h in the presence of ABPs; *TRAIL+BP, 4h* – cells incubated with ABPs for 4 hours prior to TRAIL/BP stimulation, and for 24h in the absence of ABPs). Panel C Correlation of probe inhibition potency (k_{obs}/I) toward five human apoptotic caspases and cell survival (% ratio to control). Regression coefficients (R^2) were calculated from semi-log plots, with dotted lines indicating the 95% confidence interval.